

Knowledge Of and Preventive Practices to HIV Exposure among Traditional Birth Attendants in Calabar Metropolis, Cross River State, Nigeria

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Abstract

Nigeria is listed among the Sub-Saharan African nations with 60-90% of births assisted by Traditional Birth Attendants (TBAs). The annual total births in Cross River State, Nigeria stands at 171,902 out of which 12,205 are from Human Immunodeficiency Virus (HIV) positive women, and most of these women were attended to by TBAs. The main objective of this study was to assess TBAs' knowledge of and preventive practices to HIV exposure in Calabar Metropolis. A Cross-sectional descriptive study design was used and 216 copies of an interviewer-administered questionnaire were administered, but 211(97.7%) were completed. 147(69.6%) of the respondents were between ages 40-59 years, 147(69.7%) TBAs have been trained on HIV prevention. Comparison between trained and untrained TBAs, there was a statistically significant relationship on TBAs self-reported knowledge on HIV with $P=0.003$; self-reported perceived susceptibility to HIV infection with $P=0.000$; knowledge on Prevention of mother-to-child transmission with $P=0.028$; compliance with basic preventive practices with $P=0.001$. Self-reported HIV status of TBAs revealed that 3(1.4%) were HIV positive. With a large number of untrained TBAs and even higher HIV positive pregnant women in the Calabar Metropolis posits that most TBAs stand a risk of being infected or infecting their clients. Therefore, periodic trainings of TBAs to update their knowledge on HIV prevention may improve their compliance to basic preventive practices needed in the reduction of HIV infection among TBAs and their clients.

Index Terms: Calabar Metropolis, Exposure, Human Immunodeficiency Virus (HIV), Knowledge of, Preventive Practices, Traditional Birth Attendants

I. INTRODUCTION

World Health Organisation (WHO), estimated that about 536, 000 women lost their lives yearly due to pregnancy-related causes and almost 10 million women suffer life threatening conditions and diseases that is linked to pregnancy or when giving birth to a child (WHO, 2007; Ndep, 2014). In third world countries with Nigeria as a typical example, several women are still delivering at the Traditional Birth Attendants' centre and without the help of trained medical practitioners (Mrisho, Schellenberg, Mushi, Obrist, Mshinda, Tanner & Scellenberg, 2007). A survey report shows that implementation of skilled birth healthcare services could result in the reduction of about 20-30% of newborn deaths (Darmstadt, Bhutta, Cousens, Adam, Walker & De Bermis, 2005).

Several studies have confirmed that in sub-Saharan African countries including Nigeria, between 60-90% of deliveries are attended to by Traditional Birth Attendants, with countries like Chad, Niger and Nigeria having a very large numbers of

women who are taken care of and delivered by TBAs (Okonofua & Ogu, 2014).

WHO defines a Traditional Birth Attendant (TBA) as someone that helps the pregnant mother during childbirth and who initially acquired her skills delivering babies by herself or by working with other birth attendants (Okonofua & Ogu, 2014). In the northern parts of Nigeria, TBAs are usually of the female sex only, while in some other parts of the country, they may be both males and females gender (Adesina, 2015). The number of TBAs in developing countries is not known. Conservative estimates illustrate that there is a likelihood that the number of non-skilled birth attendants will be between 180 million in sub-Saharan Africa by the end of this year, 2015 (Crowe, Utley, Costello, & Pagel, 2012). The introduction of modern medical practices tends to relegate TBA practices to the background or totally eliminate it; nevertheless, Traditional Birth Attendant is an old profession in most parts of the world especially developing countries like Nigeria. Most pregnant women register with the health facilities and attend ante-

natal care, but when it comes to the time of delivery they return to be delivered by TBAs because they believe they will be given proper care and in cases of any spiritual attacks the TBAs can save them and their children from such attacks (Sotunsa & Solademi, 2014). Some of the factors that promote women's continuous patronage of the TBAs include: the woman's level of education, employment, family income, treatment and service cost, male involvement, distance to access health facilities; attitude of health care workers, perceive danger of utilizing modern health care facilities in terms of health care workers competence to deliver services and confidence on the availability and potency of drugs and other essential commodities, religious belief and marital status (Obasi, 2013).

There are two categories of TBAs: the retired trained midwives who have worked in the formal healthcare system or have received formal training as health workers and the TBAs who acquire their skill through personal experience inherited from their mother or grandmother or might acquire the skills by learning from other elderly and experienced TBAs either formally trained or untrained. The place of TBAs cannot be ignored in the health of mothers and children in this era of HIV/AIDS since they tend to fill the gaps in maternal and child health care in rural and semi-urban Nigeria. Having this in mind, assessing Traditional Birth Attendants knowledge of his/her HIV status, the clients' HIV status, knowledge about mother to child transmission of HIV, health education as well as preventive practices including using razors and sharp objects before, during and after delivery process that exposes the Traditional Birth Attendants, women and their children to HIV infection is of utmost importance.

II.OBJECTIVES

2.1 Specific objectives

The specific objectives of this study were to;

1. determine the proportion of trained and untrained TBAs' knowledge on HIV issues in Calabar Metropolis, Cross River State
2. determine TBAs' knowledge of PMTCT
3. determine TBAs' perceived susceptibility to HIV infection

4. describe TBAs' compliance to basic preventive practices before, during and after child birth processes

III METHODOLOGY

The area chosen for this study was Calabar Metropolis comprising Calabar Municipality and Calabar South Local Government Areas, situated in the Southern Senatorial District of Cross River State. The projected population of Calabar Metropolis using the 2006 population census figure of 375,196 at 2.8% growth rate is about 500,000 people (Eni & Ukpong, 2014). The study population comprises Traditional Birth Attendants residing and practicing in Calabar Metropolis. Although previous studies have shown that most TBAs are elderly women, the study kept the age categories open to accommodate all age brackets who were residing and practicing in the area especially since the number of TBAs was not large to avoid leaving out most of the eligible ones in the study. The head of the TBA was involved in the selection of TBAs for the study. The sample size for this study was 216 TBAs, calculated based on Yamane's formula (Yamane, 1967).

A Semi-structured interviewer-administered questionnaire made-up of five (5) sections was used. A total of 216 copies of the questionnaire were administered to Traditional Birth Attendants by the principal researcher and four (4) field assistants. The four

(4) Research Assistants were recruited from two non-governmental organisations. The field assistants have been engaged in conducting research at Local, State and National levels. A two-day training was held to ensure consistency in the administration of the questionnaires and to reduce inter-interviewer bias for the current study. Data was cleaned-up and coded to ensure easy transfer from Microsoft Excel to Statistical Packages for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 20.0.

IV. RESULTS

Of the 216 copies of the questionnaire distributed, 211 were completed and returned, giving a response rate of 97.7%.

1. TBA's knowledge level on HIV

Analysis of the composite knowledge scores of TBAs' on HIV information revealed that 47(32%) of the 147 trained TBAs have high knowledge of HIV/AIDS issues, whereas only 8(12.5%) of the 64 untrained TBAs have high knowledge on HIV/AIDS. On the other hand, 51(79.7%) of the 64 untrained TBAs have average knowledge on HIV, while 97(66%) of the 147 trained TBAs have average

knowledge on HIV/AIDS (Fig 1).

Figure 1: Scores for trained and untrained TBA's knowledge on HIV

2. TBAs' Knowledge on Preventing Mother-to-Child Transmission (PMTCT) of HIV

From the composite scores, 79(53.7%) of the 147 trained TBAs and 42(65.6%) of the 64 untrained TBAs in the study had low knowledge of PMTCT. Only 17(11.6%) of the 147 trained TBAs had high knowledge on Preventing Mother-to-Child Transmission (PMTCT) of HIV; none of the 64 untrained TBAs had have high knowledge of PMTCT (Table 1).

3. Compliance to basic preventive practices

On TBAs compliance to basic preventive practices to protect themselves and their clients from exposure to HIV shows that 138(94%) of the 147 trained TBAs comply to basic preventive practices to protect themselves and their clients from HIV exposure; on the other hand, 50(78%) of the 64 untrained TBAs self report shows they comply to basic preventive prac-

tices to protect themselves from exposure to HIV (Table 2).

Table 1: TBAs' Knowledge on Preventing Mother-to-Child Transmission (PMTCT) of HIV

Variables	Un-trained (64)		Trained (147)		Total (n=211)
		%		%	
Knowledge of PMTCT					
Low Knowledge	42	65.6	79	53.7	121
Average Knowledge	1	1.6	5	3.4	6
High Knowledge	0	0	17	11.6	17
No Response	12	32.8	46	31.3	67

Table 2: TBAs' compliance to basic preventive practices against HIV infection

Variable	TBAs' Training on HIV				Total (n=211)
	untrained (64)	%	trained (147)	%	
Compliance to basic Preventive practices					
Average preventive practices	14	22	9	6	23
High preventive practices	50	78	138	94	188

V. DISCUSSIONS

A presentation made by FHI360 during a design meeting in Nigeria, stated that the 2013 National Demographic Health Survey (NDHS) report revealed that Cross River State is one of the key States in the country where most of the delivery takes place outside the formal health facility, mostly with Traditional Birth Attendants or at home ((NPC, 2014)). According to the NDHS report, more than 60% of all deliveries in Cross River State are conducted by TBAs, both trained and untrained. This is similar to the percentage (60%) in Kenya, but different as stated in an article written by nine authors in 2009 and Retrieved by Nkiruka Odunukwe in May, 2016 of a study in Lagos (90%) among the TBAs and Herbal practitioners(Ahmed et al., 2016). Therefore recog-

nizing the wide spread role of TBAs in Cross River State communities, this study was set out to examine TBAs knowledge and preventive practices in relation to HIV infection prevention.

Findings in this study showed that the age for majority of the respondents 147(69.6 %) was between ages 40-59 years. This agrees with other research which indicated that most of the TBAs are older women from ages 51 years with more than 20-40 years of experience (Seroney et al, 2012). An important revelation with this study was the fact that religion and relation to a higher being was a key factor in TBA practices as the study clearly shows that an overwhelming 210(99.5%) of TBAs were Christians and 1(0.5%) was practicing African religion. This was not taken into account by previous studies. This study revealed that in Cross River most of the TBAs were Christians, but because the Christianity was not segregated into different denomination in order to be certain why there are more TBAs in one denomination than the other, this aspect requires further study to establish fact about this issue. Nevertheless, the qualitative result indicated that irrespective of the training received by a TBA, TBA activities must always be in connection to religion or a higher being in order to provide a spiritual covering to protect the mother and child from evil attacks during pregnancy and childbirth (Ayede, 2012). This was affirmed by the head of the TBAs in Cross River State who said that during their meetings, they pray for at least one to two hours before commencing their meeting because it is God who delivers children for them. However, some of the TBAs outrightly stated that they do not need any training, attributing their decisions to total dependent on God or a higher being which they claimed has never failed them in the course of their job.

An intriguing finding from this work is that there is a high level of awareness as 209(99.1%) TBAs are aware of the existence of HIV, this is similar to an observation made by Sotunsa & Solademi (2014) on TBAs awareness level in Ogun State, 97.2%, 85% in a study in Lagos (Omowunmi & Kiru, 2004) and 65.1% in Ebonyi State (Ejikeme et al, 2007).

The Knowledge level of Traditional Birth Attendants in Calabar Metropolis on HIV as shown by this study was average with 148(70.1%) having 'average knowledge' and 8(3.8%) with 'low knowledge'

against the 55(26.1%) with 'high knowledge level' on the subject. A similar observation has been made by other authors (Peltzer & Henda, 2006) and (Seroney et al., 2012) who in their study said Trained TBAs had good knowledge on HIV than the untrained ones, but slightly higher than what was obtained in another study in Cross River State rural communities reporting those with 'average Knowledge level' at 35% and those with 'low knowledge' at 65%. This study Knowledge level was slightly lower than what was observed by Balogun et al, (2010) that the Knowledge level in Lagos was 98.1% compared to Cross River State at 35%. Cross River knowledge level of HIV at the urban centre has also risen to 96.2% for both those with 'average knowledge' at 70.1% and those with 'high knowledge' about HIV at 26.1%. In this study, this factor reflected a statistically significant difference as trained TBAs were more knowledgeable about HIV than the untrained ones. This study also revealed that TBAs perceptions on the mode of HIV transmission has improved compared to what was obtained in previous studies as 12.3% mentioned unprotected sexual intercourse; 35.1% sharing of Sharp unsterilized instruments and 26.1% could mention more than one avenue that HIV can be transmitted. This is almost similar to studies conducted in Lagos with those mentioning unprotected sexual intercourse (18%); sharp instruments sharing (36%) and no multiple responses was recorded (Seroney et al., 2012).

Furthermore, this research revealed that about 1.4% TBAs gave incorrect responses in stating other ways that HIV can be transmitted mentioning; the use of glove, dirty environment, sleeping with an older person, saliva, sweat, embracing an HIV patient tight, using condoms infected with HIV, mosquitoes bite, and through the activities of witches and wizards is worrisome and requires urgent intervention to properly educate TBAs to increase their Knowledge level and correct the myths and misconceptions being held by some of them.

The study also revealed that 39.1% of the untrained TBAs said they were less likely to contract the HIV virus; their responses suggest low susceptibility to HIV infection, but they believe other people can contract the virus. TBAs making remarks such as "HIV is a punishment from God" and that "Witches and Wizard causes HIV" shows that despite the average

and high level of knowledge on HIV as reported in this study, the responses portrays that local myths and beliefs still play a strong role in the overall understanding of the infection and transmission of HIV and should not be taken with levity (Okonofua, 2014).

This study showed that TBAs awareness of PMTCT has a slightly significant relationship with their compliance to the basic preventive practices to protect themselves and their clients from being infected with the virus. The study revealed that more than one-quarter of the TBAs 63(39.8%) are aware that HIV can be transmitted from the mother to her child during delivery and breastfeeding. This was consistent but higher than a study conducted by Madhivanan et al, (2005) which found that 36 (72%) TBAs were aware that PMTCT denotes a mother transmitting HIV to her child. However, it was lower than a report provided in a study conducted in Zimbabwe that showed that 145(68.9%) of TBAs had basic knowledge (i.e. are aware) of PMTCT (Perez et al, 2008). In this study, 36(17.1%) of TBAs could correctly state that PMTCT is preventing mother to child transmission. This was higher than that observed in a study in Lagos which revealed that only 8.3% of the TBAs interviewed had good level of knowledge about PMTCT and HIV (Balogun & Odeyemi, 2010), but it was different in a study carried out in Ogun state which showed that TBAs had high Knowledge level of PMTCT the result showing that; while more than 90% of TBAs were aware of MTCT of HIV, three out of every five of the TBAs had good knowledge of MTCT and PMTCT of HIV (Abiodun et al, 2015).

In this study it was revealed that 0.5% of the respondents mentioned breastfeeding as one way HIV can be transmitted from mother to her child. Most mothers that deliver outside the formal health facility may not be aware of their HIV status and often go ahead to breastfeed their children without wasting much time. A study conducted on Exclusive breastfeeding in Ikot Omin community in Calabar, Cross River State shows that 64% of married women practice exclusive breastfeeding and if the TBAs and the mother are unaware of their HIV status, the baby delivered is likely to be infected with the virus (Ella, Ndep, & Akpan, 2016). Also, according to Cross River operational plan, 2013-2015, PMTCT services

are not available in most facilities especially most primary health care facilities and is still very unpopular. Nevertheless, if TBAs are trained on PMTCT and HCT and allowed to offer such services considering the fact that they conduct majority of deliveries (59.1%) in Cross River State, it will go a long way in preventing the TBAs, pregnant women and their children from being infected with HIV (BSMoH, FHI360, & UNAIDS, 2013).

This study shows a significant difference between the trained and untrained TBAs in their compliance to basic preventive practices to HIV prevention. The trained TBAs were more conscious to observe the basic preventive practices and paid more attention to prevent their clients and themselves from HIV infection than the untrained TBAs. This corroborate with a study carried out in Kenya (Seroney et al., 2012) that there is a significant difference between trained and untrained Traditional Birth Attendants. The study equally revealed that there was a significant difference between the awareness of TBAs (99.1%) and their preventive practices. This could be attributed to the dosage and intensity of the HIV messages received by the Traditional Birth Attendants considering the fact that most of the information were gotten from Radio and Television (39.8%) and Health workers in the community (28.4%). This study shows that 138 (73.4%) of the trained TBAs highly comply with the basic preventive practices unlike 50(26.6%) of the untrained TBAs that said they highly complied with the basic preventive practices. There is need to train the untrained TBAs to move them to the same level of the trained TBAs.

Contrary to the observation made by Bassey et al, (2007) that was concerned with TBAs seeking to know the HIV status of their clients (2.1%) only and not their own, this study asked the TBAs if they knew their HIV status. Findings show that 88.2% of respondents knew their status, while 11.4% do not know their status. TBAs self-reported figure shows that out of the 178(84.3%) respondents that know their HIV status, only 3(1.4%) disclosed that they were HIV positive. This was almost similar to a study carried out in Copperbelt province, Zambia to assess the HIV status of TBAs, 11.9% TBAs in the study were HIV positive and those who know their status were said to be conscious of acquiring the HIV infection in the course of their work (Hazamba &

Siziya, 2010). This is because after each HIV Counseling and Testing sessions, each client is educated during the post-counseling session on how to stay negative and free from contracting the virus. Few TBAs affirmed bringing counselor testers on monthly or quarterly basis to counsel and test their clients so as to prevent them from conducting deliveries of a known HIV client; instead they refer them to the health facility for proper management. This finding is quiet interesting considering the fact that the level of stigmatization and discrimination of people living with HIV/AIDS is still very high in this locality, yet three TBAs were bold enough to disclose their HIV status as "positive" which was not the case a few years back. If three of the 211 that took part in the study could be positive, then they may be other TBAs who are positive and may not be ready to disclose this to anyone for fear of being stopped from practicing their profession. A major challenge this study found out is that most TBAs do not know their HIV status nor bother to know that of their clients and they could serve as agents of HIV infection both for their clients and themselves.

As regarding when referral is made to health facility in the case of complications, this study shows that majority 162(76.8%) of respondents make referrals when labour had lasted between three (3) hours to one day (24 hours). Although there is still room for improvement, the reported referral time is slightly higher than that of a study in Enugu where referrals are made in more than 12 hours of the active phase (36.6%) and Ebonyi when TBAs make emergency referral in more than 24 hours (Okafor et al, 2015).

There was a statistically significant difference between the trained and untrained TBAs' knowledge on HIV (Calculated Pearson Chi Square $X^2=11.597$, $P=0.003$ at 0.05 level of significance). This implies that the trained TBAs are more knowledgeable than the trained TBAs. There was also a significant difference in perceived susceptibility to HIV infection between trained and untrained TBAs (Calculated Pearson Chi Square $X^2=22.781$, $P=0.000$ at 0.05 level of significance).

The study equally shows a significant relationship between TBAs Knowledge of their HIV status and their preventive practices (Chi-square= 11.626; $P=0.001$), this is consistent with the findings of a study in Lagos that Knowledge of TBAs on HIV in-

fluences their preventive practices, but in disagreement with Ella, Ndep & Akpan's study in Kakwagom and Okundi communities in Boki Local Government Area of Cross River State, who reported that having knowledge does not translate to practice (Bhavana, 2010; Oyewo & Taiwo, 2010; Okon, 2015; Ella et al, 2016). Finally, the study indicates that there is statistically significant difference between TBAs' knowledge of HIV and their knowledge of PMTCT, as well as TBAs' knowledge of PMTCT and the compliance to basic preventive practices (Chi square = 15.537; $P=0.001$) by Traditional Birth Attendants in Calabar Metropolis.

VI. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, according to this study, the trend of delivery has not changed in Cross River State as home delivery especially those handled by TBAs still constitute a very high percentage. This study showed that TBAs awareness on HIV is high, however the knowledge level is on the average and this means there is need to educate TBAs through their networks to ensure all TBAs no matter the educational level can protect their clients and her/his self from HIV infection. This study in addition revealed that the trained TBAs were more knowledgeable than the untrained ones on HIV and as a result could protect themselves and their clients from exposure to HIV infection. This study therefore, demonstrates that TBAs awareness of preventing mother to child transmission of HIV had a statistically significant difference in the ability of the TBAs to prevent his/her self and their clients from HIV infection. Therefore, TBA leaders in the various networks should incorporate maternal and child health care including HIV, PMTCT trainings and HCT services into their monthly meeting sessions and from time to time bring in seasoned experts to train the TBAs in their domain. TBAs should also be trained and certified by the government ministries, following the Lagos state example and formally linked to the Primary health facilities or health centres close to them. This platform will contribute in educating the TBAs, debunking their myths and misconception about HIV, breaking cultural barriers and reduce their occupational risk to HIV infection as well as ensure an HIV negative woman and her child remains HIV

negative and an HIV positive mother gives birth to a child free from HIV infection if the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) targets is to be met by 2030.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

REFERENCES

- i. Abiodun, O., Sotunsa, J., Ani, F., Olaleye, A., & Taiwo A. (2015). Elimination of Mother-to-Child Transmission of HIV in Nigeria: The Roles, preparedness and Determinants of successful involvement of Traditional Birth Attendants. *J AIDS Cln Res*, 6, 481. doi: 10.4172/21556113.1000481
- ii. Adesina, S. I. (2015). Traditional Medical Care in Nigeria. from <http://www.onlinenigeria.com/health/?blurb=574>
- iii. Afangide, A. I., Njar, G. N., Ewa, E. E., Eli, H. D., & Iwara, A. I. (2011). Assessment of Water Quality Status of Borehole in Calabar South Local Government Area, Cross River State. *International Journal of Bioscience*, 1(5), 71-76.
- iv. Ahmed Omowunmi, Odunukwe Nkiru, Raheem Yekeen, Efiemokwu Chinyere, Junaid Muinat, Adesesan Segun, . . . Lateef, S. (2016). Knowledge, attitudes and perceptions of HIV/AIDS among traditional birth attendants and herbal practitioners in Lagos State, Nigeria. *African Journal of AIDS Research*, 3(2), 191–196 doi: DOI: 10.2989/16085900409490334
- v. Archibong, E. I., & Agan, T. U. (2010). Review of policies and programmes for reducing maternal mortality and promoting maternal health in Cross River State, Nigeria. *African Journal of Reproduction Health*, 14(3), 37-42.
- vi. AVERT. (2014, 2014). Origin of HIV/AIDS. Retrieved 13th July, 2015, from <http://www.avert.org/origin-hiv-aids.htm>
- vii. Ayede, A. I. (2012). Persistent Mission Home Delivery in Ibadan: Attractive Role of Traditional Birth Attendants *Annals of Ibadan Postgraduate medicine*, 10(2), 22-27.
- viii. Babette, P., Kilembe, M., & Nwateb, R. L. (1999). Report of KAP study results, Tanga region and same district, Tanzania. Retrieved 18 May, 2016, from <http://fflh.no/dialog/S5147b-KAP.html>
- ix. Balogun, M., & Odeyemi, K. (2010). Knowledge and Practice of Prevention of Mother to Child Transmission (PMTCT) Among Traditional Birth Attendants in Lagos State Nigeria. *Pan African Medical Journal*(5), 7.
- x. Bassey, E. B., Elemuwa, C. O., & Anukam, K. C. (2007). Knowledge of, and attitudes to, Acquired Immune Deficiency Syndrome (AIDS) among Traditional Birth Attendants (TBAs) in rural communities in Cross River State. *International Nursing Review*, 354-358. doi: 10.1111/ j. 1466-7657. 2007. 00535x
- xi. Bergstrom, S., & Goodburn, E. (2001). The Role of Traditional Birth Attendants in the Reduction of Maternal Mortality. . *Studies in Health Service Organisation and Policy*, 17, 85-89.
- xii. Betton, M., Bailey, C., & Safrit, J. (2013, August 26th, 2015). HIV 101: Understanding HIV. Retrieved from www.pedaids.org/blog/entry/hiv-101-understandinghiv
- xiii. Bhavana, S. (2010). Knowledge, attitude and practice of breastfeeding - a case study of Kumasi, Ghana. *European Journal of Scientific Research*, 40(3), 404-422.
- xiv. BHIVA. (2014). British HIV Association guidelines for the management of HIV infection in pregnant women, 2012. *HIV Medicine*, 15(suppl. 4), 1-77. doi: 10.1111/hiv.12185
- xv. BSMoH, FHI360, & UNAIDS. (2013). Cross River State Operational Plan for Elimination of MTCT of HIV 2013-2015. Calabar, Cross River State.
- xvi. Buldeo, P., & Gilbert, L. (2015). Exploring the Helath Belief Model and First-Year Students' Responses to HIV/AIDS and VCT at a South African University. *African Journal of AIDS Research*, 14(3), 209-218. doi: 10.2989/16085906.2015.1052527
- xvii. Buowari, B. Y. (2010). Training Workshop for TBAs at Aliero, Kebbi State, Nigeria; A

- xviii. Community Development Service at Aliero, Kebbi State, Nigeria. 7(2).
- xviii. C-Change. (2010). *Peer Educators Training Manual, Module 3- Understanding HIV and AIDS. Communication for Change, Abuja, Nigerai.*
- xix. Cambell, O. M., & Graham, W. J. (2006). *Strategies for Reducing Maternal Mortality: Getting on with what Works. Lancet, 368(9543), 1284-1299.*
- xx. CDC. (2015). *HIV/AIDS in Cameroon. 1600 Clifton Rd Atlanta, GA 30333, USA: Division of Global HIV/AIDS (DGHA), Centers for Disease Control and Prevention.*
- xxi. Crowe, S., Utley, M., Costello, A., & Pagel, C. (2012). *How Many Birth in Sub-Saharan Africa and South Asia will not be Attended by Skill Birth Attendant Between 2011 and 2015. 12, 4.*
- xxii. CRSACA, & C-Change. (2013). *Cross River State Socia and Behaviour Change Community Strategy. Calabar, Cross River State, Nigeria: USAID/C-Change project Retrieved from www.crsaca.gov.ng.*
- xxiii. Dada, B. T. (2015). *HIV Prevalence Rate in Nigeria Drops to 3.4percent. Retrieved from www.leadership.ng/news/413778/hivaids-prevalence-rate-in-nigeria-drops-to-3-4-naca*
- xxiv. Dallas, R. C., Thior, I., Kochhar, P., & Joyce, S. (2016). *Adherence: the Key Element in HIV Prevention. Retrieved from <http://thepump.jsi.com/adherence-the-key-element-in-hiv-prevention>*
- xxv. Darmstadt, G., Bhutta, Z., Cousens, S., Adam, T., Walker, N., & De Bernis, L. (2005). *Lancet Neonatal Survival Steering Team. Evidence-Based, Cost Effective Interventions: How Many Newborn Babies Can Be Save. Lancet, 365(9463), 977-988. doi: 10.1016/S0140-6736(05)71088-6*
- xxvi. Ebuehi, O. M., & Akintujoye, I. A. (2012). *Perception and Utilisation of Traditional Birth Attendants by Pregnant Women Attending Primary Health Care Clinics in Rural Local Government Area in Ogun State, Nigeria. Intl.J. Women's Health, 4, 25-34.*
- xxvii. Ejikeme, B. N., Umeora, O. U. J., & Obuna, J. A. (2007). *HIV/AIDS: awareness and practice among Traditional Birth Attendants in rural Nigeria. Nigerian Medical Practitioner, 51(1/2), 6-10.*
- xxviii. Enang, E., Ushie, M., Arikpo, I., Osonwa, K., Esu, E., Odey, F., . . . Meremikwu, M. (2013). *Childbirth Practices in the Akpabuyo Rural Health and Demographic Surveillance System. Developing Country Study, 3(8).*
- xxix. Ella, R. E., Ndep, A. O., & Akpan, M. I. (2016). *Factors Affecting Exclusive Breastfeeding Practices in Rural Communities of Cross River State, Nigeria. International Journal of Humanities Social Sciences and Education (IJHSSE), 3(4), 101-110. doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.20431/2349-0381.0304012>*
- xxx. Eni, D. D., & Ukpong, B. J. (2014). *The Impact of Population Growth on Residential Land Use in Calabar, Cross River State. Research on Humanities and Social Sciences, 4(14).*
- xxxi. Falle, T. Y., Mullany, L. C., Thatte, N., Khatry, S. K., LeClerg, S. C., Darmstadt, G. L., . . . Tielch, J. M. (2009). *Potential Role of Traditional Birth Attendants in Neonatal Healthcare in Rural Southern Nepal. J.Health Population Nutrition, 27(1), 53-61.*
- xxxii. Farlex, P. F. M. D. (2012). *Medical Dictionary for Health Professions and Nursing. from <http://medicaldictionary.thefreedictionary.com/allied+health+professional>*
- xxxiii. FHI360. (2016). *Country Design Document: Integrated Health Project in Nigeria. Abuja.5-8.*
- xxxiv. FMOH. (2005). *National Guidelines on Prevention of mother to child transmission of HIV in Nigeria.National AIDS-STI Control Programme (NASCP). Abuja, Nigeria.*
- xxxv. FMOH. (2010). *National Guidelines for Prevention of Mother-to-Child Transmission of HIV. (978-166-412-6). Nigeria.*
- xxxvi. Franny, A. (2013). *Gulu Women's Economic Development and Globalisation. from <http://www.globalgiving.org/pfil/9326/Quarterly Report April June 2013.pdf>*
- xxxvii. Gumbrecht, J. (2015). *Cuba Ends Mother-to-Child Transmission of HIV and Syphilis [Press release]. Retrieved from*

- www.edition.cnn.com/2015/07/01/health/cub
a-hiv-mother-child-transmission
- xxviii. Igherase, G. O., & Ebeigbe, P. N. (2007). Maternal mortality in rural referral hospital in the Niger Delta, Nigeria. *J Obstet Gynaecol*, 27(3), 275-278.
- xxxix. Imogie, A. O., Agwubike, E. O., & Aluko, K. (2002). Assessing the Role of Traditional Birth Attendants in Healthcare Delivery in Edo State Nigeria. *African Journal of Reproduction Health*, 6(2), 94-100.
- xl. Israel, G.D. (2013). Determining sample size, University of Florida IFAS Extension, Gainesville, FL32611 Revised April, 2009. Revised June, 2013 <http://edis.ifas.ufl.edu.PEOD6>
- xli. Lawn, J. E., Cousens, S., & Zupan, J. (2005). 4 Million Neonatal Death When ? Why ? *Lancet*, 365(9464), 891-900.
- xlii. Madhivanan P., Kumar B.N., Adamson P., & K., K. (2010). Traditional birth attendants lack basic information on HIV and safe delivery practices in rural Mysore, India. *BMC Public Health*. doi: 10.1186/1471-2458-10-570
- xliii. Mandal, A. (2015). History of AIDS. *News Medical*. from <http://www.news-medical.net/health/History-of-AIDS.aspx>
- xliv. Mbiydzennyuy, N. E. (2012). Traditional Birth Attendant: Filling the Black Space in Rural Cameroon Midwife. *International Training the Next Generation of Midwives.*, from <http://midwifeinternational.org/how-to-become-midwife/traditional-birth-attendants-incameroon/>
- xlv. Mrisho, M., Schellenberg, J. A., Mushi, A. K., Obrist, B., Mshinda, H., Tanner, M., & Scellenberg, D. (2007). Factors Affecting Home Delivery in Tanzania. *Tropical Medicine and International Health*, 12(7), 862-872.
- xlvi. NACA. (2014). Federal Republic of Nigeria Global AIDS Response Country Progress Report (GARPR) (pp. 1-46). Abuja, Nigeria: National Agency for the Control Of AIDS.
- xlvii. NARHS. (2013). HIV prevalence Across the State. Abuja, Nigeria: National Agency for the Control of AIDS.
- xlviii. Nasidi, A., & Harry, T. O. (2006). The Epidemiology of HIV/AIDS in Nigeria (pp. 17-36). Retrieved from www.apin.harvard.edu/chapter2.pdf
- xlix. Ndep, A. O. (2014). Informed Community Participation is Essential to Reducing Maternal Mortality in Nigeria. *International Journal of Health and Psychology Research*, 2(1), 26-33.
- l. NIH. (2015). Understanding HIV/AIDS. Nigeria: National Institute of Health Retrieved from <https://www.niaid.nih.gov/topics/hiv/aids/understanding/pages/default.aspx>.
- li. NIMH. (2015). What is Prevalence? Bethesda, USA: national Institute of Mental Health Press Retrieved from www.nimh.nih.gov/health/statistics/prevalence/index/sh.
- lii. Nkwo, P. O. (2012). Prevention of Mother-to-Child Transmission of Human Immunodeficiency Virus: The Nigerian Perspective. *Annals of Medical and Health Science Research*, 2(1), 56-65.
- liii. NPC. (2014). Nigeria Demographic and Health Survey 2013. Abuja, Nigeria and Rockville, Maryland, USA: National Population Commission and ICF International.
- liv. Obasi, E. Z. (2013). A Review of the Barriers and Socio-cultural Factors Influencing the Access to Maternal Health Care Service in Nigeria. (Master Degree Review), Helsinki Metropolia University of Applied Science.
- lv. Okafor I.I., Arinze-onyia, S. U., Onyekpa, J. I., & Ugwu, E. O. (2015). Audit of Childbirth Emergency Referrals by Trained Traditional Birth Attendants in Enugu, Southeast, Nigeria. *Ann. Med. health sci. res.*, 5(4), 305-310. doi: 10:410/2141-9248.160180
- lvi. Okon, E. B. (2015). Factors affecting exclusive breastfeeding practice in Ikom town, Cross River State, Nigeria. *Bachelor of Public Health*, University of Calabar
- lvii. Okonofua, F., & Ogu, R. (2014). Traditional Versus Birth Attendants in Provision of Maternity Care: Call for Paradigm Shift. *African Journal of Reproduction Health*, 18(1), 11-15.

- lviii. Omowunmi A., Nkiru O., Yekeen R., Chinyere E., Muinat J., Segun A., . . . S., L. (2004). Knowledge, attitudes and perceptions of HIV/AIDS among traditional birth attendants and herbal practitioners in Lagos State, Nigeria. *Afr. J. AIDS Res.*, 3, 191-196. doi: 10.2989/16085900409490334
- lix. Oshonwoh, F. C., Nwakwuo, G. C., & Ekiyor, C. P. (2014). Traditional Birth Attendants and Women's Health Practice: A Case Study of Patani in Southern Nigeria. *Journal of Public Health and Epidemiology*, 6(8), 252-261. doi: 10.5897/JPHE2013.0634
- lx. Osuji, A., Pharr, J., Nwokoro, U., Ike, A., Ali, C., Ejiro, O., . . . Ezeanolue, E. (2015). Impact of HIV Testing and Counseling, Knowledge on HIV Prevention Practices Among Traditional Birth Attendants in Nigeria. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 12(2), 1969-1982. doi: 10.3390/ijerph 120201969
- lxi. Oyewo, T. O., & Taiwo, N. (2010). Exclusive Breastfeeding in Lagos: An awareness case study. *Mass Communicator*. 4(2), 20-29.
- lxii. Peltzer, K., & Henda, N. (2006). TBAs HIV/AIDS and safe delivery in the Eastern Cape, South Africa-evaluation of a training program. *SAJOG-South African journal of obstetric and gynaecology*, 12(1), 140-145.
- lxiii. Perez, F., Aung, K., Ngoro, T., Engelsmann, B., & Dabis, F. (2008). Participation of Traditional Birth Attendants in Preventing Mother-to-Child Transmission of HIV services in two rural districts in Zimbabwe: a feasibility study. *BMC Public Health*. doi: 10.1186/1471-258-8401
- lxiv. Seroney, G. C., Minnie, K., Otieno-Ayayo, Z. N., Mulaudzi, F. M., & Nyangena, E. (2012). KNOWLEDGE, ATTITUDES AND PRACTICES OF TRAINED TRADITIONAL BIRTH ATTENDANTS ON HIV/AIDS, KENYA. *Baraton Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 2(1), 8 - 16.
- lxv. Sibley, L. M., Sipe, T. A., & Barry, D. (2012). Traditional Birth Attendant Training for Improving Health Behaviour and Pregnancy Outcomes (Review). *CD005460*(8), 1-82. doi: 10.1002/14651858.CD005460.Pub3
- lxvi. Simpson, B. (2008). World Class Research on Slim Disease. *Journal of Public Health*, 30(12), 54-63.
- lxvii. Siziya, S., & Hazemba, A. (2010). Occupational risk factors for HIV infection among Traditional Birth Attendants in Copperbelt province, Zambia. *African J Health Sci.*, 17, 5-9.
- lxviii. SNLN. (2011). *Newborn Health in the Context of the Integrated Maternal, Newborn and Child Health Strategy* (2nd ed., pp. 1-120). Saving Newborn lives in Nigeria.
- lxix. Sotunsa, J. O., & Solademi, O. B. (2014). Determination of Education Needs of Traditional Birth Attendants on the Prevention of Mother to Child Transmission of HIV in Ogun State, Nigeria. *Quarterly*. www.jara.adelekeuniversity.edu.ng
- lxx. Stretcher, V. J., & Rosenstock, I. M. (1997). *The Health Belief Model*. In Andrew Baum. *Cambridge Handbook of Psychology, Health and Medicine*. Cambridge UK: Cambridge University Press.
- lxxi. TAI. (2011). Where did HIV come from. Washington DC: National Policy Office Retrieved from <http://www.theaidsinstitute.org/aids-101/where-aid-hiv-come-o>.
- lxxii. Titaley, C. R., Hunter, C. L., Dibley, M. J., & Heywood, P. (2010). Why do some Women Still Prefer Traditional Birth Attendants and Home Delivery?: a Qualitative Study on Delivery Care Services in West Java Province, Indonesia. *BMC Pregnancy Childbirth*, 10, 43. doi: 10.1186/1471-2393-10-43
- lxxiii. Trans, M., & Stoppler, M. C. (2015). HIV/AIDS Facts. Retrieved from http://www.emedicinehealth.com/hivaids/page3_em.htm
- lxxiv. UNAIDS. (1999). *Prevention of Mother to Child Transmission: Strategic Option*. 20 Avenue Appia-1211 Geneva 27 Switzerland: UNAIDS Retrieved from <http://www.unaids.org>.
- lxxv. UNAIDS. (2013). *Global report: UNAIDS report on the global AIDS epidemic 2013*. 20 Avenue Appia-1211 Geneva 27-Switzerland UNAIDS.

- lxxvi. *UT. (2015). Health Belief Model. Retrieved 15th September, 2015, from https://www.utwente.nl/cw/theorieenoverzicht/Theory%20Clusters/Health%20Communication/Health_Belief_Model/*
- lxxvii. *Vanguard. (2012, August 13th). Seventy Thousand Babies HIV Positive Annually, Nigerian Vanguard (Mobile Edition).*
- lxxviii. *WHO. (2005). The World Health Report (2005). Make Every Mother and Child Count.*
- lxxix. *WHO. (2007, 1st October). Prevention of Mother-to-Child Transmission (PMTCT) [Briefing Note]. Briefing Note. Geneva, Switzerland.*
- lxxx. *WHO. (2010). Classifying Health Workers.*
- lxxxii. *WHO. (2010). PMTCT strategic vision 2010–2015 : preventing mother-to-child transmission of HIV to reach the UNGASS and Millennium Development Goals. Geneva, Switzerland World Health Organisation.*
- lxxxiii. *WHO. (2012). Maternal Mortality. Fact Sheet. Retrieved 348*
- lxxxiii. *WHO. (2015). Mother-toChild Transmission of HIV. Retrieved July, 16th, 2015, from HIV/AIDS Department World Health Organisation www.who.int/hiv/topics/mtct/en/*
- lxxxiv. *WHO. (2015). WHO Validates Elimination of Mother-to-Child Transmission of HIV and Syphilis in Cuba [Press release]. Retrieved from www.who.int/mediacentre/news/release/2015/mtct-hiv-cuba/en/*
- lxxxv. *WorldBank. (2003). Reducing Maternal Mortality, Learning from Bolivia, China, Egypt, Honduras, Indonesia, Jamaica and Sri Lanka. Human Development Network, Health Nutrition and Population Series. Washington DC.*
- lxxxvi. *Yamane, T.(1967). Statistics: An Introductory Analysis, 2nd Edition. New York: Harper and Row. http://kb.psu.ac.th/psukb/bitstream/2010/6023/6/260491_ch3.pdf*